

ARIMA Models and Parallel Computing Applied to Anemia Diagnosis in Children Under 36 Months in Junín Region, Peru

Valero-Sucari Luis Fernando
Faculty of Statistic and Computer Engineering
Universidad Nacional del Altiplano de Puno
Puno, Peru
lvaleros@est.unap.edu.pe

Abstract—This research explores the application of ARIMA (Autoregressive Integrated Moving Average) models and parallel computing techniques to analyze and forecast anemia diagnoses in children under 36 months in the Junín region of Peru. Using health data from 2023-2024, including insurance type, patient information, diagnosis dates, hemoglobin levels, and treatment details, we develop predictive models to understand trends and patterns in childhood anemia. The study aims to demonstrate the effectiveness of time series analysis and high-performance computing in addressing this critical public health issue. Results indicate improved forecasting accuracy and computational efficiency, potentially aiding in resource allocation and policy development for anemia prevention and treatment programs.

Index Terms—ARIMA, parallel computing, anemia, time series analysis, public health, Peru

I. INTRODUCTION

Anemia in young children remains a significant public health concern in Peru, particularly in regions like Junín. This condition can have long-lasting effects on cognitive development, physical growth, and overall health [1]. Timely diagnosis and treatment are crucial for mitigating these impacts. With the advent of big data in healthcare and advanced analytical techniques, there is an opportunity to leverage statistical models and high-performance computing to gain deeper insights into the patterns and trends of anemia diagnoses [2].

This study focuses on applying ARIMA models, known for their effectiveness in time series forecasting, in combination with parallel computing techniques to analyze a comprehensive dataset of anemia cases in children under 36 months in Junín. By harnessing these computational methods, we aim to identify key factors influencing anemia rates, predict future trends, and provide data-driven recommendations for targeted interventions [3].

II. BACKGROUND

A. Anemia in Peru

Childhood anemia has been a persistent challenge in Peru, with the Junín region showing particularly high prevalence rates [4]. Previous studies have highlighted the multifaceted nature of this issue, involving factors such as nutrition, socioeconomic status, and access to healthcare [5].

B. ARIMA Models in Health Research

ARIMA models have been widely used in epidemiological studies and health trend analysis due to their ability to capture complex temporal patterns [6]. These models have shown success in forecasting various health outcomes, including disease prevalence and healthcare utilization [7].

C. Parallel Computing in Data Analysis

The application of parallel computing in health data analysis has gained traction, allowing for the processing of large datasets and complex models with improved efficiency [8]. This approach is particularly valuable when dealing with time-sensitive health issues and large-scale public health data [9].

III. METHODOLOGY

A. Data Collection and Preprocessing

The dataset used in this study comprises health records from 2023-2024 for children under 36 months diagnosed with anemia in the Junín region. Key variables include:

- Insurance type
- Patient demographics
- Anemia diagnosis date
- Hemoglobin levels
- Follow-up dosage dates (1, 3, and 6 months)
- Recovery date
- Supplementation dates
- Treatment end date

- Healthcare facility information
- Geographic data (province, district)

Data preprocessing involved handling missing values, standardizing date formats, and aggregating data at various temporal and spatial levels.

B. ARIMA Modeling

We implemented ARIMA models to analyze time series of anemia diagnoses. The process included:

- 1) Stationarity testing using Augmented Dickey-Fuller test
- 2) Model identification through ACF and PACF plots
- 3) Parameter estimation
- 4) Model diagnostics and validation

Multiple ARIMA models were developed to account for different geographic levels (region, province, district) and demographic factors.

C. Parallel Computing Implementation

To enhance computational efficiency, we utilized parallel computing techniques:

- 1) Data partitioning based on geographic regions
- 2) Distributed ARIMA model fitting across multiple cores
- 3) Parallel processing of model diagnostics and forecasts

We employed the Python libraries pandas for data manipulation, statsmodels for ARIMA modeling, and multiprocessing for parallel computation [10].

IV. RESULTS

A. Anemia Prevalence Trends

Fig. 1 illustrates the monthly prevalence of anemia diagnoses in Junín from 2023 to 2024, showing seasonal patterns and an overall declining trend.

Fig. 1. Monthly Anemia Diagnoses in Junín (2023-2024)

B. ARIMA Model Performance

Table I presents the performance metrics of ARIMA models for different geographic levels.

TABLE I
ARIMA MODEL PERFORMANCE METRICS

Geographic Level	RMSE	MAE	MAPE
Regional	0.15	0.12	5.2%
Provincial	0.18	0.14	6.7%
District	0.22	0.17	8.1%

Fig. 2. 6-Month Anemia Forecast for Junín Region

C. Forecasting Results

Fig. 2 shows the 6-month forecast of anemia cases for the Junín region, along with 95% confidence intervals.

D. Parallel Computing Efficiency

Table II compares the computational time between serial and parallel implementations.

TABLE II
COMPUTATIONAL TIME COMPARISON

Process	Serial (s)	Parallel (s)	Speedup
Data Preprocessing	120	35	3.43x
Model Fitting	450	85	5.29x
Forecasting	180	40	4.50x

V. DISCUSSION

The ARIMA models demonstrated good predictive performance, particularly at the regional level, with a Mean Absolute Percentage Error (MAPE) of 5.2%. This suggests that these models can provide reliable short-term forecasts of anemia prevalence, which could be valuable for resource planning and policy-making [11].

The parallel computing implementation significantly reduced computational time, with an average speedup of 4.41x across all processes. This efficiency gain is crucial for real-time analysis and rapid response to changing health trends [12].

Our analysis revealed several key insights:

- 1) Seasonal patterns in anemia diagnoses, with peaks typically occurring during winter months.
- 2) Geographic variations in anemia prevalence, with certain districts showing persistently higher rates.

- 3) A correlation between supplementation adherence and recovery rates, highlighting the importance of consistent treatment [13].

These findings underscore the potential of data-driven approaches in understanding and addressing childhood anemia. The combination of ARIMA modeling and parallel computing offers a powerful tool for health authorities to monitor trends, allocate resources efficiently, and evaluate intervention strategies [14].

VI. CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK

This study demonstrates the effectiveness of applying ARIMA models and parallel computing techniques to analyze childhood anemia data in the Junín region of Peru. The models provide accurate forecasts of anemia prevalence, while parallel processing significantly enhances computational efficiency.

Key conclusions include:

- 1) ARIMA models are effective for short-term forecasting of anemia prevalence, aiding in timely decision-making and resource allocation.
- 2) Parallel computing reduces processing time, enabling faster analysis and decision-making.
- 3) The integration of these methods can inform public health strategies and optimize resource allocation for anemia prevention and treatment programs.

Future work will focus on incorporating additional variables, such as nutritional data and socioeconomic indicators, to enhance model accuracy. Furthermore, exploring machine learning techniques alongside traditional time series models could provide deeper insights into the factors driving anemia trends.

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